

Transmetalation as Key Step in the Diastereo- and Enantioselective Synergistic Cu/Pd-Catalyzed Allylboration of Alkynes with Racemic Allylic Carbonates

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ABSTRACT.

Cu/Pd-catalyzed alkyne allylboration with racemic allylic carbonates proceeds with total inversion of configuration. Preliminary studies show that this synergistic catalysis can be used to perform a dynamic asymmetric allylic alkenylation that provides enantioenriched carboboration products.

TEXT

INTRODUCTION

Transition metal catalyzed allylic substitution reactions represent powerful and versatile tools for the formation of C–X and C–C bonds.¹ In particular, Pd-catalyzed allylic substitution of chiral racemic allylic substrates has been extensively studied and has found diverse applications in the synthesis of natural products and bioactive compounds.² Two distinct mechanistic pathways

operate for this type of reaction depending on the nucleophile employed. Nucleophiles classically classified as “soft” undergo external anti attack to the key π -allyl-Pd(II) intermediate, generated via stereoinvertive oxidative addition, thus resulting in a net retention of the configuration (Scheme 1A).³ Conversely, the use of “hard” nucleophiles such as main group organometallic compounds generally leads to an overall inversion of configuration as a result of a transmetalation to the Pd center followed by reductive elimination (Scheme 1A).⁴ Stabilized or “soft” carbon nucleophiles which typically include malonate derivatives or those derived from pronucleophiles with $pK_a < 25$ have received major attention in Pd-catalyzed allylic substitution.² Recent reports by Trost⁵ and Walsh⁶ have shown that basic carbanions derived from BF₃-bound 2-methylpyridines,^{5a,b} methyl polynitrogen-heterocycles,^{5c} Cr-(CO)₃-toluene complexes,^{6a,b} and even diarylmethanes^{6c} also behave as “soft” nucleophiles, raising the pK_a limit of this type of pronucleophiles to at least 32. The use of nonstabilized “hard” nucleophiles in Pd-catalyzed allylic substitution has been less explored,^{4,7} and only few examples of asymmetric allylic alkylation (AAA) involving allyl boronates⁸ and dialkylzinc reagents⁹ have been reported so far.¹⁰ To the best of our knowledge, the Pd-catalyzed asymmetric allylic alkenylation with “hard” C(sp²) nucleophiles remains elusive,¹¹ described.¹² We recently reported a synergistic Cu/Pd-catalyzed allylboration of alkynes with bis(pinacolato)diboron (B₂pin₂) and allylic carbonates.¹³ This transformation involves the catalytic generation of a β -boryl-alkenylcopper species by addition of a CuBpin complex across an alkyne and subsequent Pd-catalyzed allylic substitution to formally constitute a carboboration reaction.¹⁴ Attractive features of this method are that a simple alkyne is used as precursor for a catalytically generated alkenylmetal reagent, thus allowing to keep a low concentration of the reactive species, and that new C–C and C–B bonds are generated in a single operation. Following on these studies, we decided to investigate the

performance of our dual catalytic system in the allylboration of alkynes with cyclic racemic allylic carbonates (Scheme 1B). Although organo-copper reagents have been identified as “soft” nucleophiles in their direct reactions with allylic substrates,¹⁵ little is known about their nucleophilic nature in Pd-catalyzed allylation reactions.¹⁶ While copper enolates have been reported to behave as “soft” nucleophiles in Cu/Pd-catalyzed alkylation of chiral allylic substrates,¹⁷ the behavior of alkenylcopper nucleophiles in this type of reactions is unknown. Herein we report the exploration and stereochemical outcome of the Cu/ Pd-catalyzed allylboration of alkynes as well as our preliminary results on the asymmetric enantioconvergent version.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To assess whether the catalytically generated alkenylcopper species behave as “soft” or “hard” nucleophile in the Pd-catalyzed allylation event, a range of different terminal and internal alkynes **1** were reacted with diastereomerically pure *cis* allyl carbonates **2** and B²pin² (**3**) under our previously optimized conditions¹³ (Scheme 2). Reactions proceeded with near perfect chemo- and regioselectivity and total stereospecificity in all cases and exclusively furnished the corresponding products **4** in very good yields. Excellent diastereocontrol was observed, with *cis* allyl carbonates **2** providing the corresponding products **4** as single *trans* diastereomers. Similarly, when pure *trans* cyclic allyl chloride **5** was reacted with 3-ethynylthiophene and B₂pin₂ under our Cu/Pd catalytic conditions only *cis*-**4d** was obtained. These results clearly indicate that the catalytically generated β -borylalkenylcopper intermediate behaves as a “hard” nucleophile in this transformation. At this point, we were eager to investigate an asymmetric variant of this transformation that could enable the deracemization of cyclic allylic substrates through a DYKAT type II process^{2,18} and the generation of valuable enantioenriched cyclic

systems bearing a synthetically versatile alkenyl boronate group. It is important to note that, while catalytic asymmetric multicomponent carboboration processes of different unsaturated hydrocarbons with prochiral electrophiles have been reported,¹⁹ carboboration reactions involving an enantioconvergent transformation of a racemic substrate represent an uncharted territory.²⁰ Initial studies using a combination of CuCl/PCy₃ with Pd catalysts made from a range of chiral mono- and bidentate phosphines already showed the challenging nature of this multicomponent reaction. Pd catalysts derived from ligands typically used in Pd-catalyzed AAA reactions such as Trost or Phox ligands, Feringa-type phosphoramidites or ferrocene-based biphosphines led exclusively to degradation of **2a** through B₂pin₂ allylation pathways^{21,22} (see Supporting Information, Table S1). Surprisingly,²³ only the use of (*R,R*)-DIOP **L1** provided the desired product **4a** in significant yield. Further investigations using this ligand revealed that the use of a polar solvent was crucial to turn the reaction enantioselective, with DMA providing the best selectivity (Table 1).

Evaluation of different Cu and Pd catalysts and leaving groups further revealed important features of this transformation (Table 2). We observed that the nature of the Cu catalyst affects not only the efficiency of the reaction but also its enantioselectivity (entries 1–7). Although the use of Tol-BINAP did not lead to the highest er at 50 °C, it was the only one that allowed to lower the reaction temperature while retaining the conversion and the excellent levels of chemo- and regioselectivity. By using this ligand at 30 °C, we obtained **4d** in 68% yield with an increased er of 78:22 (entry 9). Reactions using enantiopure (*R*)- and (*S*)-Tol-BINAP provided only slight variations on the yield and enantioselectivity (entries 6– 8), thus discarding a possible match/mismatched scenario between both chiral catalysts for enantioinduction.²⁴ The leaving group of the racemic allyl substrate also played a key role both in efficiency and the

enantioselectivity of the reaction. The use of a tert-butyl carbonate led to a very sluggish reaction, and no desired product could be obtained (entry 10). Similarly, the corresponding allyl phosphate or acetate did not lead to any conversion (entries 11–12). Interestingly, *trans*-allyl chloride **5** could be transformed into *cis*-**4d** in very good yield by using our chiral catalytic system, although the product was obtained as a nearly racemic mixture (entry 13). Finally, we investigated different Pd complexes derived from DIOP analogues in combination with the Cu/Tol-BINAP catalyst (entries 14–19). The poor *er* values observed for ligands **L2–4** indicated that changing the bite angles of DIOP derivatives by altering the acetal backbone has a significant impact on the enantioselectivity. A variety of substitutions for the acetal backbone were tested, and a slight improvement was achieved by using (*R,R*)-Cp-DIOP **L5** which afforded **4d** in 73% isolated yield and with 80:20 *er*. These conditions could also be applied to other racemic allylic carbonates and alkynes, obtaining similar *er* values and excellent levels of chemo-, regio-, and diastereoselectivity in all cases (Scheme 3). On the basis of our experimental observations, a mechanism in which both catalytic cycles are connected by transmetalation between intermediates **I** and **II** may be proposed (Scheme 4). Production of optically active products **4** would result from enantiodiscrimination of the allylic termini in **II** and subsequent reductive elimination in **III**. The results obtained from the optimization studies reflect the importance of an efficient equilibration to the symmetrical pseudo-meso- π -allylPd(II) intermediate **II** prior to the transmetalation step in order to achieve an enantioselective process. While polar solvents facilitate its formation by ion pair separation, in nonpolar solvents allyl-Pd(II) intermediate might exist as a mixture of diastereomeric σ - or π -allyl tight ion pairs²⁵ which could react with **I** before equilibration, thus compromising the chiral recognition imposed by the ligand. Similarly, with the more coordinating chloride as a leaving group (Table 2, entry 13),

reaction may be occurring through this type of intermediates. The different *er* values observed upon change of the Cu catalyst might be due to different rates of transmetalation which in some cases could be of similar order of magnitude as the rate of symmetrization of allyl intermediate II. Another possible explanation would involve a bimetallic transition state being responsible for the enantioselection, although the absence of match/mismatch effects makes this option less likely.

CONCLUSION

In summary, we have developed a diastereo- and enantioselective Cu/Pd-catalyzed allylboration of alkynes with racemic allyl carbonates. The observed total inversion of configuration suggests that catalytically generated alkenylcopper species act as “hard” nucleophiles in the Pd-catalyzed allylation step. Preliminary results show the potential application of Cu/Pd-catalyzed carboboration reactions in dynamic kinetic asymmetric transformations. Further studies to gain insight on the reaction mechanism and to extend this methodology to related systems are underway.

FIGURES

Abstract

Scheme 1. Stereospecific Coupling of C(sp²) Nucleophiles with Racemic Allylic Substrates

(A) Stereospecific coupling with pregenerated Csp² nucleophiles

(B) Stereospecific coupling with catalytically generated Csp² nucleophiles (this work)

Scheme 2. Diastereoselective Cu/Pd-Catalyzed Allylboration of Alkynes(a)

Scheme 3. Enantioconvergent Cu/Pd-Catalyzed Allylboration of Alkynes(a)

a. Reactions run on a 0.3 mmol scale. Yields refer to isolated products. b L5 was used. c L1 was used.

Scheme 4. Proposed Mechanism

Table 1. Effect of Solvent on the Enantioselectivity of the Cu/Pd-Catalyzed Allylboration of Alkynes.

entry	solvent	4d (%) b	6d (%) b	4d er c
1	toluene	92	8	58:42
2	THF	99	–	57:43
3	MTBE	30	50	60:40
4	DCE	50	20	63:37
5	CH ₂ Cl ₂	25	–	65:35
6	acetonitrile	30	23	69:31
7	DMF	40	25	73:27
8	DMA	62	7	74:26

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

*s1 Supporting Information: The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.organomet.0c00010>. List of starting materials, synthetic procedures, and characterization data (PDF)

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